

CLOSTRIDIODES DIFFICILE U BOLNIČKIM USLOVIMA

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CLOSTRIDIODES DIFFICILE IN HOSPITAL SETTINGS

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Protekle decenije su bile svedok značajnog globalnog porasta incidencije i težine infekcije *Clostridioides difficile* (*C. diff*). Ovaj patogen je dugo bio među najopterećenijim bolničkim infekcijama, ali je sada postao vodeći faktor koji doprinosi oboljevanju i mortalitetu od zaraznih bolesti u razvijenim zemljama. Infekcija se najčešće dobija u bolnici, a potencijalno se može sprečiti strategijama koje imaju za cilj minimiziranje prenosa između pacijenata ili smanjenje osetljivosti pacijenata, prvenstveno smanjenjem neodgovarajuće upotrebe antibiotika, a posle i primenom drugih preventivnih mera.

Abstract

The past decades have witnessed a significant global increase in the incidence and severity of *Clostridioides difficile* (*C. diff*) infection. This pathogen has long been among the most burdensome hospital infections, but it has now become a leading factor contributing to morbidity and mortality from infectious diseases in developed countries. The infection is most commonly acquired in hospitals and can potentially be prevented through strategies aimed at minimizing transmission between patients or reducing patient susceptibility, primarily by decreasing inappropriate antibiotic use, followed by the implementation of other preventive measures.

Cljučne reči: *Clostridioides difficile*, bolničke infekcije, antibiotici.

Keywords: *Clostridioides difficile*, hospital infections, antibiotics.

Clostridioides difficile

During the 19th century, pseudomembranous colitis was described in the literature as a complication of gastroenterostomy. In the early 1970s, the study of this condition increased due to its frequent and sometimes fatal association with the use of certain antibiotics. It was determined that pseudomembranous colitis is an infectious condition caused by an organism named *Clostridioides difficile* [1].

C. difficile is a gram-positive, spore-forming, anaerobic bacterium that is the most common cause of antibiotic-associated diarrhea in healthcare systems of the developed world. *C. difficile* infections can be categorized as endogenous and exogenous. Endogenous infection occurs through carrier strains, while exogenous infection occurs through infected individuals, contaminated healthcare workers, hospital sources, and contaminated environments.

C. difficile infection (CDI) spreads via the fecal-oral route. Besides direct contact, transmission is also

possible through indirect contact: on high-touch surfaces in the room of infected/colonized patients (e.g., bed rails, doorknobs, bedside tables), by using reusable equipment between patients (electronic thermometers, stethoscopes), and by transferring spores from healthcare workers to uninfected patients.

CDI occurs by the oral ingestion of spores, which are resistant in the environment and tolerant to stomach acidity. In the small intestine, ingested spores germinate into the vegetative form. Additionally, the use of antimicrobial agents and disruption of normal colonic bacteria leads to the colonization of *C. difficile* in the colon. Subsequently, bacterial growth, multiplication, and toxin production damage the intestinal crypts.

The primary toxins produced by this bacterium are toxin A (enterotoxin) and toxin B (cytotoxin). Although evidence suggests that toxin A is the main toxin, *C. difficile* strains that produce toxin B cause the same spectrum of diseases as strains that produce both toxins. Additionally, toxin A (TcdA) and toxin B (TcdB) are the

main virulence factors of *C. difficile* that have contributed to its pathogenicity [2].

Risk Factors

Understanding the risk factors for CDI is essential for determining appropriate preventive measures to reduce infection. Various known risk factors include:

- Patient age (>64 years);
- Use of broad-spectrum antibiotics or prolonged antibiotic therapy;
- Patients with extended hospital stays or those in nursing homes;
- Immunocompromised individuals (HIV/AIDS, patients undergoing chemotherapy);
- Concurrent comorbidities (e.g., inflammatory bowel disease);
- Gastrointestinal procedures;
- Use of nasogastric tubes, etc.

Clinical Presentation of *C. difficile*

According to clinical criteria, the diagnosis of *C. difficile* is based on an appropriate clinical context, a history of recent antibiotic use, and diarrhea. Other important diagnostic signs include fever, abdominal pain, leukocytosis, and pyrexia in combination with laboratory testing. In severe cases, *C. diff* infection can lead to life-threatening dehydration (from fluid loss due to diarrhea), low blood pressure, a condition called toxic megacolon (acute colon dilation requiring surgery), and colon perforation.

Recently, the Society for Healthcare Epidemiology of America (SHEA) and the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA) have published guidelines for treating patients with CDI. According to their guidelines, all laboratory tests should be performed on unformed stool samples unless ileus is suspected [3].

Due to the presence of both toxigenic and non-toxigenic strains of *C. difficile* in asymptomatic patients, testing is not necessary for infected or recovered individuals. Additionally, processing a single sample from a symptomatic patient is usually sufficient. There are many different diagnostic tests for identifying *C. difficile* infection. It is important to be aware of the limitations of each test and the need to follow protocols for proper sample selection and handling.

Hospital-acquired infection is defined as the onset of symptoms more than 48 hours after admission to a healthcare facility or less than 4 weeks after discharge. However, a significant percentage occurs in individuals who have not received antibiotic therapy nor have been recently hospitalized. This group is recognized as community-acquired infection, defined as the appearance of symptoms in the community or within the first 48 hours after hospital admission, provided there has been no hospitalization in the past 12 weeks. The onset of symptoms occurring in the community between 4 and 12 weeks after hospital discharge is defined as indeterminate infection.

Epidemiology

In the past two decades, the incidence and mortality rate of *C. difficile* have significantly increased in both hospital and community settings due to the spread of hypervirulent strains and improper antibiotic use [4]. The incidence of infection began to rise in the early 2000s. The epidemiology of the infection in North

America, Europe, and some parts of Asia is well documented. Based on several reports from the USA, Canada, and Europe, the incidence has increased by 2 to 4 times in the last decade, particularly among older patients who have been exposed to healthcare facilities. Quebec is known for its high incidence rate, which has increased fourfold in the past 13 years, with a mortality rate of 6.9%. Europe has not been spared either. The European Study Group for *C. difficile* (ESGCD) reported a median incidence of healthcare-associated infections of 4.1 per 10,000 hospital days [5]. In 2008, the United Kingdom reported 55,502 cases of affected individuals, while Germany reported slightly more, with 58,000 cases in the same year. The Republic of Serbia classifies CDI as a common hospital-acquired infection. Supporting this, in 2009, the Clinical Center of Serbia treated 250 individuals, with a mortality rate of 7.2% [5].

Treatment

Treatment of CDI is not recommended for asymptomatic individuals, as available data suggest that treating asymptomatic persons would not prevent infection. Different treatments are applied based on the severity of the patient's illness and whether it is an initial infection or recurrent CDI.

Treatment in cases of CDI is classified into two main categories: non-surgical and surgical treatments. Non-surgical treatment, or short-term antibiotic therapy, is clinically effective for a small percentage of patients, but specific antimicrobial therapy is necessary for the majority of patients. The use of agents such as narcotics and loperamide is not recommended, as they can increase the severity of colitis. Empirical antibiotic therapy in patients with severe diarrhea and at-risk populations should be initiated immediately while waiting for stool test results. Metronidazole and oral vancomycin are recommended as antibiotics for treating the initial episode. Metronidazole, as a cheap and effective first-line drug with low resistance levels and few side effects, is used for treating mild to moderate disease orally or intravenously, but should not be used for critically ill patients [6]. Unlike vancomycin, metronidazole is well absorbed, and its fecal concentration is very low or absent in healthy volunteers and asymptomatic *C. difficile* carriers.

Surgery is a therapeutic option for treating fulminant colitis or patients who do not respond to medical therapy. For patients who do not respond to optimal medical therapy or have symptoms of megacolon or sepsis, early surgical consultation is recommended. In early cases of fulminant colitis, any delay in surgery can be fatal [6]. An abdominal CT scan can provide valuable information in assessing the severity of the disease and the need for surgical intervention.

Prevention

Efforts to prevent initial CDI, especially in healthcare settings, are essential. The foundation of these efforts includes reducing prolonged use of multiple antibiotics and preventing transmission from patient to patient. Major preventive measures include the proper and recommended use of antibiotics, contact precautions, appropriate hand hygiene, and the use of

sporicidal agents for cleaning and disinfecting the environment.

It is important to implement antibiotic stewardship guidelines. Every prescribed antibiotic should adhere to local treatment and prophylaxis guidelines (based on local sensitivity profiles), and broad-spectrum drugs should be avoided. The indication should be documented along with the date when the treatment should be stopped or reassessed. The shortest effective course of treatment should be prescribed, and prescriptions should be reviewed daily to assess the need and ensure the use of the narrowest-spectrum antibiotic.

C. difficile is transmitted via spores caught either through indirect contact with a contaminated surface or direct contact with an infected person (likely through hands in hospital settings). In recent years, it has been established that surface and equipment contamination plays a key role in the transmission of *C. difficile* infection between patients. The spore form of *C. difficile* is considered the vehicle for CDI transmission [6]. Some strains are believed to show a greater ability to sporulate than others. The use of sodium hypochlorite, chlorine dioxide products, and chlorine solutions has proven effective in killing *C. difficile* spores. However, alcohols, chlorhexidine, hexachlorophene, and many disinfectants routinely used in antiseptic handwashing agents or cleaning solutions have been shown to be ineffective against *C. difficile* spores [7].

Handwashing before and after contact with patients suspected or confirmed to have *C. difficile* infection is essential, as is wearing personal protective equipment when caring for patients and handling clinical samples. The hands of healthcare workers are one of the important routes of transmission for *C. difficile*. Healthcare workers must wash their hands with soap and water to mechanically remove spores from their hands. Although many challenging studies have believed that handwashing with soap and water (or antiseptic soap) is more effective than alcohol-based hand rubs for removing *C. difficile*, the use of alcohol-based hand rubs is still an effective way to reduce the overall incidence of healthcare-associated infections [7].

Early isolation of patients with diarrhea is necessary to reduce airborne spread and environmental contamination.

Conclusion

CDI is a serious healthcare problem with increasing incidence worldwide that can cause significant morbidity and mortality. Considering the rising incidence of CDI even in populations previously considered to be at low risk, as well as identifying at-risk populations, monitoring incidence, and characterizing the molecular epidemiology of strains, it is essential for healthcare institutions and scientific societies to reassess their national infection control surveillance. Proper use of antibiotics and contact precautions, such as glove use, handwashing, and environmental disinfection, along with integrated surveillance programs, can be effective in controlling CDI outbreaks. Adherence to evidence-based basic precautions can quickly reduce the transmission of *C. difficile* and associated mortality. Surveillance is essential for assessing the effectiveness of interventions.

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